

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

STRATEGIC TOOLS FOR ENHANCING THE INVESTMENT APPEAL OF CONSTRUCTION COMPANIES

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Abstract

The relevance of developing and applying strategic tools to ensure the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises has been established.

Further refinement is required in the development and implementation of strategic tools to ensure the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises.

The study has achieved its objective of identifying strategic tools to ensure the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises.

Strategic tools for ensuring the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises have been proposed. A roadmap has been developed, which includes areas for increasing the integrated indicator by ensuring positive shifts in factors related to overcoming the consequences of hostilities, assessing the status and functioning of construction enterprises and the sector, overall, the management of stakeholder relations, the implementation of approaches and specific features for ensuring investment and environmental activities, and the utilisation of investment and innovation resources, taking security parameters into account. This has enabled the development of measures to enhance the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises, the formation and utilisation of investment and innovation resources, and to improve the soundness of management decision-making.

An organisational and economic mechanism for building the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises is proposed for the development and implementation of a stakeholder-oriented strategy; this is an open system based on the creation and application of economic and organisational components, the interaction of which is aimed at increasing the level of investment attractiveness. The necessity of applying SWOT and PEST analysis has been identified.

Keywords: investment attractiveness, construction companies, strategy, strategic tools, organisational and economic mechanism, roadmap.

Introduction. Investment attractiveness (IA) characterises the state of an enterprise, reflecting its investment potential and the extent to which it generates and utilises investment resources, as well as its interaction with various stakeholder groups aimed at the development of business entities. At the present stage, there is a slowdown in growth or a decline in the level of investment attractiveness of construction enterprises (CE). These processes are exacerbated by the growing direct damage to infrastructure caused by the aggression, amounting to \$170 billion [1].

The residential sector has been hardest hit, with direct losses estimated at \$60 billion; specifically, 236,000 residential buildings have been damaged or destroyed, of which 209,000 are private homes, 27,000 are apartment blocks, and 600 are student halls of residence. The regions of Donetsk, Kharkiv, Luhansk,

Kyiv, Chernihiv and Kherson have suffered the most extensive damage

[1].

The regulatory framework, which has been adapted in response to the ongoing hostilities and which affects the operations of construction companies, encompasses the following areas: determining construction costs; establishing and maintaining a repository of building standards; entities responsible for standardisation in the construction sector; carrying out standardisation work in the construction sector during a period of martial law; changes to regional development programmes during martial law; changes to urban planning documentation during martial law; specific features of the application of national standards for construction products; the development and implementation of a

comprehensive regional recovery programme; the development and implementation of a comprehensive recovery programme for a local authority area (or part thereof); ensuring public consultation on draft comprehensive recovery programmes [2]; identifying those entitled to compensation for damaged or destroyed immovable property; applying the procedure for compensation for destroyed immovable property; determining the amount of compensation for destroyed property; compiling a register of damaged property [3].

Factors hindering the effective functioning of the construction sector include: construction delays: due to hostilities, landmines and a shortage of resources, many projects have been put on hold or cancelled. This is particularly true of regions where active hostilities are still ongoing or have recently come to an end [4]; Shortages of labour and materials: due to mobilisation, migration and the disruption of supply chains, the sector is facing a shortage of skilled workers and building materials; the need for new standards: reconstruction requires adaptation to new realities – in particular, improving the resilience of buildings to attacks, creating shelters, enhancing energy efficiency and ensuring rapid assembly.

To address these challenges, the development and implementation of strategic tools to ensure the investment attractiveness of construction companies is of paramount importance.

Justification of existing theoretical approaches.

Academic works have identified key areas and highlighted the characteristics of the development and application of strategic tools to ensure investment attractiveness. Significant attention is focused on specific strategies. A company's development strategy is defined as either active or passive, each with its own characteristics: risks, innovation, competitors, sales and product policy, and market share [5]. Key features of the formulation and implementation of corporate development strategies [6].

The following classification criteria for a company's strategy have been identified, namely:

- areas of management and the specific features of its implementation;
- the company's operational life cycle;
- market behaviour;
- the creation of competitive advantages [7].

In addition, the following strategies are identified: corporate, business, functional and operational [8]. Depending on the approaches used to formulate the strategy and its functional purpose, they are classified as: global strategies, portfolio strategies and functional strategies [8]. It has been determined that a strategy needs to be developed to ensure the long-term operation of enterprises

It has been established that a strategy is required for the long-term operation of enterprises [9].

The works focus on the areas of resource development and utilisation for the implementation of the strategy [10].

The strategy aims to secure competitive advantages for businesses, and sets out the methods, models and tools for developing and achieving them [11].

An algorithm is proposed for developing a development strategy for construction enterprises, which includes: strategic analysis of construction enterprises' activities (identifying external changes occurring in the environment of construction enterprises; characterising the competitive environment of construction enterprises; identifying internal processes within construction enterprises; identifying shortcomings in the existing strategy); justification of the strategic objectives of construction enterprises; selection of alternative strategies based on strategic analysis and the identification of strategic development objectives; development of a plan for implementing the construction enterprise's strategy; timely introduction of necessary changes to the chosen enterprise strategy as a result of external factors; ongoing adjustments to the developed strategy depending on the influence of internal factors; monitoring of strategy implementation [12].

The formulation of a development strategy for construction companies in wartime depends on the availability of resources, innovation and investment processes, the application of modern organisational, financial and economic tools, and the identification of opportunities for achieving strategic objectives [12].

To develop a growth strategy for construction companies, their strengths and weaknesses have been identified, opportunities and threats assessed, and the factors influencing the construction sector analysed using SWOT and PEST analyses.

A suitable model is applied to implement a stakeholder-oriented strategy [13]. In particular, the risks arising from its use are identified: technical, financial and economic, human, legal, social and environmental [14].

At the same time, the development and implementation of strategic tools to ensure the investment attractiveness of construction companies require further refinement.

The aim of the study is to identify strategic tools for ensuring the investment attractiveness of construction companies.

Main section. Roadmaps are used as strategic tools. The development of a roadmap for implementing a stakeholder-oriented strategy to enhance the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises is based on the results of mathematical modelling and forecasting. The potential for developing and applying roadmaps in enterprises is highlighted in academic works [15, 16].

The following classifications of strategic maps have been identified:

- depending on the purpose of development and implementation: product planning; planning capabilities and capacity; strategic planning; investment resource planning; intellectual asset planning; programme planning; process planning; integrated planning;
- depending on the type: sectoral; corporate; operational; corporate; technological; scientific; programme;
- depending on the graphical format: multi-level; columnar; tabular; graphical; flowcharts; single-level [17].

It has been established that a fundamental change in the indicators set out in the roadmap is characterised by a transformation in the approaches to their formulation, the paradigm of their application, changes to the information and analytical support for economic and mathematical modelling, and a significant level of utilisation of the relevant resources that underpin these areas. The level of stakeholder interaction and the application of mechanisms for its implementation are of particular importance.

Scientific works emphasise the creation of scenarios for the functioning of economic systems [18].

The development and implementation of a scenario-based approach in accordance with the relevant legislation are set out in the following regulatory documents: Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine «On the Development of Forecast and Policy Documents for Economic and Social Development and the Preparation of Drafts of the Budget Declaration and the State Budget» № 621 of 26 April 2003, Order of the Ministry of Regional Development, Construction and Housing and Communal Services of Ukraine «On the Approval of the Methodology for the Development, Monitoring and Evaluation of the Effectiveness of the Implementation of Regional Development Strategies and Action Plans for their Implementation» № 79 of 31 March 2016.

Proposed scenarios for shaping the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises: pessimistic, stabilisation, transition and development.

An organisational and economic mechanism has been developed, which is an open system comprising a set of elements forming the organisational component (an organisational unit whose functions include ensuring the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises, and the development and implementation of measures to ensure investment attractiveness) and an economic component (elements for establishing a quantitative basis and developing scenarios). The organisational and economic mechanism is an important component in the development and implementation of a stakeholder-oriented strategy for enhancing the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises.

Conclusions. Thus, a strategic toolkit has been proposed to ensure the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises. A roadmap has been developed which includes areas for improving the integrated indicator by ensuring positive changes in factors related to overcoming the consequences of hostilities, assessing the status and functioning of construction enterprises and the sector, as a whole, fostering stakeholder relations, implementing approaches and specific measures to support investment and environmental activities, and utilising investment and innovation resources, whilst taking security parameters into account. This has enabled the development of measures to enhance the level of investment attractiveness of construction enterprises, the formation and utilisation of investment and innovation resources, and to improve the soundness of management decision-making.

An organisational and economic mechanism for enhancing the investment attractiveness of construction

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